

Paper 16

GEOPOLITICS AND ITS IMPACTS ON INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS DECISIONS

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ABSTRACT

Geopolitics is a technique of studying FOREIGN POLICY to understand, explain and predict international political behavior through geographical variables. Together with other environmental variables, they also influence a firm's decisions on its future or existing international business activities.

Key Words: Geopolitics, Impact, Country, Business, Operation, Environmental.

1. INTRODUCTION:

The term *Geopolitics* was first coined by *Rudolf Kjellén*, a Swedish political scientist, at the beginning of the 20th century. The doctrine of *Geopolitics* gained attention largely through the work of *Sir Halford Mackinder* in England and his formulation of the *Heartland Theory* in 1904. Ancient India had its own great geopolitical scientists. One most astonishing example seems to be that of Chanakya, (3rd century BC), the great teacher, a great politician and a person who really had a great regional view. His geopolitical understanding was very deep which helped him to unit a number of independent states on the Indian continent and around given the lack of communication, education, infrastructure of his time. Geopolitics is the relationship between the political power and geographic space. The drivers of change for the geopolitical environment are time, location and demography. These also provide guidance towards revealing the pervasive nature of geography and its impact upon other environmental-specific variables, e.g., local politics and culture [1]. The main purpose of this study is to understand the political and strategic significance of a geographic space when defined in terms of – Location, Size, Workings, Culture and Resources.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

The core objective of this study is to understand the overall perspective of Geopolitics provides the link between geography and strategy. Geopolitics is based on the undeniable fact that all international politics, running the gamut from peace to war, takes place in time and space, in particular geographical settings and environments. Geopolitics publishes work on traditional topics like interstate relations, great powers relations, global institutions, regional integration, territorial control and access to energy, resources and trade routes, and state borders.

3. THE ROLE OF GEOPOLITICAL VARIABLES IN INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS OPERATIONS:

Geopolitical variables have been playing an important role in conditioning the international business environment. The geopolitical environment continues to unfold [2]. Apart from geographic distance and location, variables include the consequences of colonial, Cold War and post-Cold War outcomes, regionalization, population characteristics, the distribution of the global population and their impacts on international business operations.

(a) Place Dimension: From the geopolitical perspective, relationships among states are influenced by an area's strategic value (Cohen, 1963). Deeply engrained ideologies can further shape the institutional comparative advantages and disadvantages of certain firm types in host countries [4]. This value, however, depends on the importance of an area in terms of its natural resources, size and future prospects in relation to other countries. For example, Australia's relationship with New Zealand bears more strategic value than its relationship with Sri Lanka. Because of the geographic proximity of Australia to New Zealand, their relationship in terms of each other's political, economic and security interests is more critical than Australia's relationship with many other countries.

(b) Time Dimension: The international distribution of power among states shifts continually as one historical period gives way to another (Wallerstein, 1980, in Dougherty & Pfaltzgraff, 1990). The international geopolitical environment has been changing constantly (Cohen, 1963) affecting international business dynamics. The negative effect of GPR on capital structure decisions is more pronounced during periods of high freight rates, high economic growth, and tranquillity [5]. Any specific change in this environment at a particular point of time may influence the operations of international business within, as well as beyond, that time frame. It is important for the international business firm to monitor these changes and to respond to them accordingly and in a timely manner.

4. EFFECT OF GEOPOLITICAL ENVIRONMENT ON A REGIONAL LEVEL OVER POLITICAL, ECONOMIC AND IDEOLOGICAL SYSTEM:

In this line of thinking some very interesting arguments emerged are as follows. India has one of world's strongest soft powers (political say). Many countries find it important to have smooth relations with India for their geopolitical situations. Globalization, hyper-competition between multinational enterprises (MNEs), and proliferation of non-state stakeholders is making the context of global business increasingly complex [6]. For example:- in spite of the fact that India has a leaning towards Iran, both Israel and US cannot afford to be on the wrong side with India, because of soft power of India and realization that India has sovereign right to be friendly with nations which has potential to safeguard India's future energy requirements. India's leaning towards Iran is not just confined to get energy security it also aims at bringing US on negotiating terms in the wake of growing military aid to Pakistan, which is being used against India. South Sudan, the newest nation of the world which has world backing. The responses of economic growth have shocks on FDI, inflation, and trade openness [7]. There are places which are still fighting to be free and self-governing. Perhaps the geopolitical fortunes of such nations are not as promising as has happened to South Sudan. Purple Revolution of the Middle East, if it spreads to China, can be a shortterm disadvantage for China but it has the potential to bring lots of Geopolitical gains for the world's most populous country.

5. CURRENT GEOPOLITICAL OBJECTIVES OF INDIA:

With China, progressive steps should be undertaken to demilitarize the Line of Actual Control (LAC) with the incentive of bulk cross border trade and building transportation infrastructure. India should sign a defence co-operation agreement with the Myanmar government to secure the Indo-Myanmar border areas especially along the economic corridors from drugs and small arms networks. India's engagements with Nepal and Bhutan have to focus on economic development with increasing strategic dialogue with the emerging importance of both countries as buffer countries. Pakistan, complete border dominance should be achieved, especially along the Line of Control (LOC), plus full-proof infiltration surveillance and interdiction capabilities. With Russia, India must work towards building new energy business relationship while expanding traditional areas of defence and space and further strengthen India-Russia strategic partnership in Afghanistan in concert with Iran for bringing about stability and development in Afghanistan. Sri Lanka would require high level visits as gestures for bringing back diplomatic ties to an even keel. It is critical that India restarts stalled economic engagements with Sri Lanka. Coming to the US, India should expand and strengthen the civil nuclear relationship for generating alternate sources of energy in the common geo-political ground scenario in Asia as well as boost the US-India defence relationship and military ties for greater inter-operability in counter-terrorism. With Iran, India should establish strong strategic ties vindicated by a country rich in culture, civilization, and resources and encourage Iran to play a stabilizing role in the Middle East. While identifying these countries do not mean that others don't matter—for instance building stronger economic ties with Europe, Africa, and Latin America should be of priority. India must showcase its leadership role, broadcast its capabilities and ambitions, issue directions on what are its foreign policy priorities through the publication of policy 'white papers' on defence, economy, strategy, etc., and take a stand on issues of global concern, including the health of the world's environment, conflicts in Africa and the Middle East, and transnational crime.

6. WORLD ECONOMIC SITUATION AND PROSPECTS 2018:

(a) Prospects for Global Macroeconomic Development: Stronger economic activity has not been shared evenly across countries and regions. As headwinds from the global financial crisis subside, policymakers have more scope to tackle longer-term issues that hold back sustainable development. Investment conditions have improved, but elevated policy uncertainty and rising levels of debt may prevent a more widespread investment rebound. Rebound in world trade could face a setback if protectionist tendencies increase

(b) Progress towards Sustainable Development: Weak growth in per capita income poses setbacks to sustainable development targets in several regions. Supporting growth in LDCs requires both financial resources and progress towards addressing institutional deficiencies and security concerns. Accelerated economic growth increases need to consider links to environmental sustainability. Transition towards sustainable energy remains gradual. From a global perspective, governance structures of an individual country can be influenced by the governance prerogatives of another country or a global institution with legitimate authority.[8]

(c) **Uncertainties and Risks:** Economic prospects remain vulnerable to changes in trade policy, a sudden deterioration in global financial conditions and rising geopolitical tensions.

7. MOU's SIGNED DURING 2018:

India signed MOU with	Purpose of the MOU
India and Myanmar	On Land Border Crossing
India and Italy	Cooperation in the field of renewable energy
India and Israel	Cooperation in the oil and Gas Sector
India and Belgium	Cooperation in the field of ICT&E
India and Transport for London	To improve Public Transport in India
India and UK	For the return of illegal Indian Migrants, sharing of criminal records
Rajasthan and HDFC Bank	Tie up to help start-ups
India and Saudi Arabia	Haj Agreement
India and Canada	For Cooperation on Science and Technology
Gujarat and South Korea	For Business Cooperation
India and Sri Lanka	4 Agreement for Collaboration in ICT Sector
India and Israel	<p>sign 9 MoU's to boost cooperation in various fields on cyber-security cooperation</p> <p>MoU on Protocol between India and Israel on Amendments to the Air Transport Agreement</p> <p>MoU between the Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas and the Ministry of Energy on Cooperation in Oil and Gas Sector.</p> <p>MoU on filmmaking</p> <p>collaboration in the field of medicine</p> <p>MoU with Technion- Israel Institute of Technology</p> <p>MoU for exchanging information on investment opportunities, relevant laws and regulations, policies and government initiatives</p> <p>For cooperation in the area of metal-air batteries.</p> <p>For cooperation in the area of concentrated solar thermal technologies.</p>

ASSOCHAM and Football Delhi	To Strengthen Commercial Profile
India, Vietnam	On I&B, Space Cooperation
India, Cambodia	Ink four pacts to Strengthen Bilateral Ties
India and Seychelles	To build Military Infrastructure on Assumption Island
Andhra Pradesh-Zurich	Sign Sister State Agreement
Water resources Ministry signed MOU with Bihar and Jharkhand	For completion of North Koel reservoir project
Johnson & Johnson partners with Maharashtra government	On Health Interventions
Punjab gov. inks MOU with IOC	To set up Biogas, Bio-CNG plants
Centre, Jammu and Kashmir	For Education Reforms
NITI Aayog and Andhra Pradesh government	To develop an Online Dashboard
Telangana government signed MOU with the Clean Authority of Tokyo	For Municipal Solid Waste Incineration

8. GEOPOLITICAL TENSIONS WHICH WILL CONTINUE OVER THE YEARS:

Across the globe, governments and institutions face increasing challenges to their legitimacy and authority. All forms of government in every region will face increasing tensions both domestic and foreign. Sharpening tensions and heightened doubts concerning the U.S. role in the world will continue for several years. The European Union will need to implement badly needed reforms to maintain its legitimacy. In Northeast Asia, growing tensions around the Korean Peninsula are likely, with the possibility of a confrontation in the coming years. The United States' traditional partners, Europe and Japan, would increasingly be challenged to maintain economic growth in view of their aging populations.[9]. Populism and dissent will spread across Latin America. Expect increasing assertiveness from Beijing and Moscow as both governments seek to lock in competitive advantages. The standoff between Russia and the West will Continue throughout 2017 and 2018. Violent extremism, terrorism, and instability will continue to hang over Afghanistan, Pakistan, and the region's fragile communal relations. Sub-

Saharan Africa will struggle with authoritarian regimes. Threats from terrorist and insurgent groups will persist and are likely to become more decentralized.

9. SUGGESTIONS:

It is the responsibility of the CEO and board of directors to look ahead and protect their company from catastrophic disruptions, nationalizations and other geopolitical calamities. These executives rarely seem to have much more success in looking ahead than the managers who report to them. Part of the problem is that it is often tough for corporate leaders to find the time to dig deeply into the historical and modern issues of the countries in which their companies operate. One solution may be to engage board members in periodic scenario-planning workshops in which they consider important geopolitical events that might occur within the next decade or two. Using this model, a corporate board that holds a one-day workshop each year focusing on different regions of the world would cover, in five to seven years, the entire planet. For this process to work, however, it is important to ensure that board members have the requisite training and experience to delve deeper into the realm of geopolitics and use their insight to steer their companies toward a safer course.

10. CONCLUSION:

In geopolitics there are no permanent friends or enemies, only enduring interests. India's interests are clear: to preserve the multilateral trading order while improving its own global competitiveness and ability to deal with a structured world economic order where no one country is any longer able to define global rules. The geopolitical environment in international business consists of a set of political factors and government activities in a foreign market that can either facilitate or hinder a business' ability to conduct business activities in the foreign market. The critical approach provides a needed and necessary critique of the classical, exposing its weaknesses and suggesting an emancipatory alternative [10]. There is often a high degree of uncertainty when conducting business in a foreign country. To manage longer-term risks like these, companies must look further and act accordingly. This means spending money today to prepare for the possibilities tomorrow may bring, however unwelcome they might be. Building slack resources such as industrial overcapacity or safety stocks into supply chains, taking out expensive insurance policies, or both will be necessary.

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